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Different kinds of embodied language: a comparison between Italian and
Persian languages

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Abstract

It is debated whether only concrete but also abstract, figurative sentences, e.g.: “She grasps the cup” vs. ”She grasps the concept”, are grounded in the sensorimotor system. Importantly, studies on sentences with action verbs and motor system activation have been conducted so far only with WEIRD samples (Western cultures, in North American and European countries). The aim of our work is to investigate the relationship between language and motor responses using both concrete and abstract sentences in Italian and Persian languages. In the present study, Italian and Persian participants were asked to read the sentences on the screen. The sentences referred either literally or metaphorically to motor actions. They were accompanied by a video displaying a movement that could be congruent or incongruent with the one described in the sentence. Participants were asked to re-execute the movement observed and subsequently they had to perform the task evaluating whether the sentence made sense or not. In the Italian sample a strong effect of concreteness was present, especially in the congruent but also in the incongruent condition. In the Persian sample, instead, there was an inhibition effect of congruent trials, particularly with concrete sentences, and in the incongruent trials no difference in RTs between abstract and concrete sentences was present. Results indicate that cross-cultural differences have to be taken into account when investigating the relationship between language and action.

Keywords: WEIRD, action, sentences, cultures, language grounding, embodied cognition

58 **Highlights:**

- 59 ● Culture modulates the cross-talk between language and action
- 60 ● In the Persian sample, when an action observed and performed is compatible with the action
61 expressed in a sentence induces an inhibition of the motor response in a sentence sensibility
62 task, especially when the sentence is concrete.
- 63 ● In the Italian sample abstract sentences are processed faster than concrete ones
64 (concreteness effect)
- 65 ● In the Italian sample (WEIRD), when an action observed and performed is compatible with
66 the action expressed in a concrete sentence it induces a tendency towards the facilitation of
67 the motor response in a sentence sensibility task

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70 **1. Introduction**

71 Do people of different cultures comprehend action related language in a different way?

72 The fact that action words and sentences recruit sensorimotor information is quite an established
73 finding. Many consolidated research lines address this issue. Here we will focus on three of them,
74 i.e. the studies on the relationship between action verbs and involvement of effectors, the studies on
75 the Action Sentence Compatibility (ACE) effect, and the studies on the spatial interference effect.
76 Importantly, most studies within these research lines were conducted with Western participants. We
77 will now briefly describe these research lines, and propose a study in which action-language
78 integration is investigated with a cross-cultural approach.

79 **1.1 Action verbs and effectors.** When we process action verbs and sentences entailing action
80 verbs, we implicitly activate the effector to which the words refer. Seminal EEG and fMRI studies
81 have demonstrated that different areas of the brain are activated when reading verbs referring to
82 different effectors, such as ‘kick’, ‘lick’, ‘pick’ (Hauk, Johnsrude, & Pulvermüller, 2004;
83 Pulvermüller, Härle, & Hummel, 2001; Tettamanti et al., 2005), and that part of the brain is
84 activated in a somatotopic way. Results obtained with transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) are
85 contrasting. With a combined TMS and behavioral study Buccino et al. (2005) found a decrease in
86 amplitude of MEPs recorded from hand muscles while listening to hand-action-related sentences
87 (e.g. s/he sewed the skirt), and from foot muscles when listening to foot-related sentences (e.g. s/he

88 kicked the ball). This finding is quite robust, even if not always replicated (Gianelli & Dalla Volta,
89 2015). Other TMS studies (Oliveri et al., 2004; Pulvermüller, 2005) and behavioral studies show a
90 facilitation: for example, Scorolli & Borghi (2007) found a facilitation when reading sentences
91 related to the foot and to the mouth and concurrently producing a response with the implied
92 effector. Behaviorally, reading the sentence “he/she sewed the skirt” yielded longer response times
93 with hand than with foot responses system, while the opposite was true for sentences such as
94 “He/she kicked the ball”; interference was also found by Sato et al. (2008), but only with tasks
95 implying deep semantic processing and not with more shallow lexical decision tasks. Overall, the
96 most consistent pattern of results seems to show an early interference (but Gianelli and Dalla Volta
97 (2015) and Pulvermueller (2005) found an early facilitation) in case of congruency between the
98 effector implied by the verb and the one used to respond, and a late facilitation (but Sato, 2008, did
99 not find it). In any case, all results converge in showing the action-language cross-talk. In recent
100 work Miller et al. (2018) performed 8 experiments in which they combined behavioral with ERPs
101 tasks. They found a facilitation in RTs in case of congruency between the effector implied by the
102 sentence and the one involved to respond, but the ERP (Event-related Potentials) analyses showed
103 that ERPs differed for hand versus foot movements, but not for hand- versus foot-associated words.
104 This invites to be cautious as it might suggest that language-related compatibility effects on RTs
105 might emerge before action processing, hence might not be determinant for language
106 comprehension.

107 **1.2 ACE effect.** Glenberg and Kaschak (2002) were the first to demonstrate the Action Sentence
108 Compatibility (ACE) effect: when participants process sentences referring to a movement away
109 from or toward their body (e.g. “open/close the drawer”), responses are facilitated in case of
110 congruency between the action implied by a sentence and a real movement, away or toward the
111 body, performed to respond. The typical ACE task is a sentence sensibility evaluation one, in which
112 participants are required to decide whether the sentence makes sense or not – the effects hold
113 however with a variety of slightly different tasks, such as evaluation of words (part vs. no part), and
114 sentence sensibility evaluations (Borghi, Glenberg, & Kaschak, 2004; Kaup, Lüdtke, & Maienborn,
115 2010), and for a variety of linguistic phenomena (e.g. sentences, words, sentences describing a
116 state, (Kaup et al., 2010). The ACE effect is not exempt from criticism: recently Papesh (2015) has
117 questioned the strength of the ACE effect, showing though Bayesian analyses that only a minority
118 of the published results offer strong evidence for the ACE; one of the problems pointed out by the
119 authors is that some studies lead to a facilitation and some to an interference effect.

120 **1.3 Spatial interference effect.** When visual stimuli instead of only words are presented, a reversed
121 effect is obtained, i.e. no facilitation but an interference is reported. Estes and Barsalou (2018)
122 found the spatial interference effect, an effect of attention on language, showing that processing
123 words with spatial associations (e.g., “bird”, “hat”) can reduce the capability to identify an
124 unrelated visual target (e.g., X) at the implied location (i.e., at the top of a display). Even if the
125 reliability of the effect was criticized, Estes and Barsalou (2018) reported a meta-analysis of 37
126 studies indicating that the effect was reliable. They collapsed studies using single words or
127 sentences, in which the task was to detect the visual target and the target was unrelated to the
128 words.

129 Overall results from the three lines of research we have outlined reveal that the meaning of the
130 language is intimately tied to the actions it refers to. However, the results obtained are not always
131 coherent. There is certainly a crosstalk between language and action, but some studies report that
132 language processing interferes with action execution while others find a facilitation (notice that
133 similar facilitation and interference effects are also found in the action observation literature (Brass,
134 Bekkering, & Prinz, 2001). Different explanations of these contrasting results have been advanced.
135 The most common is based on timing (e.g. Borreggine & Kaschak, 2006; de Vega, Moreno, &
136 Castillo, 2013), and it has been explained with a model (Chersi, Thill, Ziemke, & Borghi, 2010) that
137 predicts interference when action and language are simultaneously processed, and facilitation in
138 case of delayed processing. Another explanation, which is not necessarily mutually exclusive with
139 the first, points to the ease of integration between the sentence meaning and the motor action/visual
140 stimuli: when the integration is scarce, then interference occurs (Kaschak et al., 2005).

141 **1.4 Action verbs in literal and figurative sense.** While numerous studies have demonstrated a
142 tight relationship between language and motor system, only a small subset of studies have
143 investigated whether action sentences still recruit sensorimotor information when used in an
144 abstract sense. For example, if we hear or read the sentence “He does not grasp the concept”, do we
145 still activate the grasping movement? The more relevant to our aims are studies that investigate
146 grounding of figurative language, and particularly those that concern non-idiomatic, novel
147 metaphors/abstract usage. Most results show that also figurative sentences involve areas engaged in
148 processing concrete sentences, and thus are grounded in the sensorimotor system (e.g. Boulenger,
149 Hauk, & Pulvermüller, 2008; Boulenger, Shtyrov, & Pulvermüller, 2012; Desai, Binder, Conant,
150 Mano, & Seidenberg, 2010; Mano et al., 2012; Saygin, McCullough, Alac, & Emmorey, 2009;
151 Wallentin, Østergaard, Lund, Østergaard, & Roepstorff, 2005). There are, however, inconsistencies:
152 some neuroimaging studies found motor/premotor activation for literal but not for figurative

153 sentences (Aziz-Zadeh, Wilson, Rizzolatti, & Iacoboni, 2006; Raposo, Moss, Stamatakis, & Tyler,
154 2009). Specifically, Desai et al. (2013) showed that motor activation increased at the reduction of
155 abstractness and conventionality of sentences. At a behavioral level, Scorolli et al. (2011)
156 investigated response times using simple sentences resulting from combinations of concrete and
157 abstract verbs/nouns (e.g. think of/caress the dog/idea). Mixed combinations led to longer response
158 times, especially when the concrete word preceded the abstract one: this shifting cost can be
159 ascribed to the hypothesis that concrete and abstract words are processed in parallel systems, one
160 more linguistic and the other more sensorimotor, in line with the hypothesis of the WAT (Words As
161 social Tools) theory (Borghi et al., 2019; Borghi, Barca, Binkofski, & Tummolini, 2018); this
162 hypothesis is supported by two further fMRI and TMS studies with the same stimuli (Sakreida et
163 al., 2013; Scorolli et al., 2012).

164 **1.5 Action-language cross-talk in different cultures.** The aim of our work is to investigate the
165 relationship between language and motor responses using both concrete and abstract sentences in
166 two different languages, Italian and Persian. To the best of our knowledge, studies on the
167 relationship between sentences with action verbs have been conducted so far only with WEIRD
168 (Henrich, Heine, & Norenzayan, 2010a, 2010b) participants, i.e. participants of Western cultures, in
169 North American and European countries. The only exception we are aware of is a study by
170 Dennison & Bergen (2010) that showed that social and cultural practices influence the way people
171 represent action language. They focus on a social practice common in Korean culture, in which
172 people tend to use both hands to give objects to people of higher social status. The authors
173 manipulated the status of the recipient of the presented sentences, using sentences such as “You are
174 now giving a letter to (your) professor / to (your) younger sibling”. The acquired cultural practice is
175 reflected in the ACE effect found: consistently with the acquired behavior, when presented with
176 sentences referring to transfer of an object to high status recipients Korean participants were slower
177 in bimanual responses, while unimanual responses were slower with sentences referring to low
178 status recipients.

179 Even if this study shows the tight relation language-action in an Eastern culture, it does not compare
180 Eastern and Western cultures using the same task. This is instead what we did in the present work.

181 Here, we used sentences that referred either literally or metaphorically to motor actions, with no
182 directional information. They were accompanied by a video displaying a movement that could be
183 congruent or incongruent with the one described in the sentence. Participants were asked to
184 reproduce the movement observed in the video, then they had to perform the task evaluating
185 whether the sentence made sense or not. We wanted to render the task as much implicit as possible,

186 hence we opted for asking participants to perform a sentence sensibility judgment rather than
187 requiring participants to evaluate the congruency between the action and the sentence. Since the
188 displayed actions could involve the hands, we asked participants to respond by pressing a pedal
189 when the sentence made sense and to refrain from responding when it did not: it was thus a go-nogo
190 paradigm. Response times and accuracy were recorded. The reason why we decided to show
191 participants a video and ask them to perform the observed movement is that we intended to boost
192 motor activation, in order to verify its relationship with language processing.

193 To investigate whether the relationship between language and movement was the same across the
194 two different languages/cultures, we submitted the same task to Italian and Iranian participants.
195 Notice that these two cultures are likely not extreme in their Western/Eastern characteristics: for
196 example, Italian culture is less individualistic than US culture (Henrich et al., 2010b), Iranian
197 culture likely differs from East-Asian cultures on a variety of dimensions. Evidence has shown that
198 belonging to a Western or an Eastern culture influences a variety of cognitive processes, starting
199 from perception to decisional processes (review in Henrich et al., 2010b): Asian people tend to
200 perceive the environment in a more holistic way, Western cultures are generally more analytic
201 (Nisbett & Masuda, 2003); sense of agency differs as well - Western people tend to perceive events
202 as the outcome of a choice more often than Eastern people (Savani, Markus, & Conner, 2008).
203 Similarly to other Asian cultures, Iran can be considered as a collectivist culture (Hofstede, 1980),
204 as testified by the presence of extended families, by the important role played by the ingroup, by the
205 strong sense of national belonging, and also by some linguistic habits such as the frequent use of the
206 pronoun “we” instead of “I” (Zampour & Zadri, 1996). Because of the strong differences between
207 typical WEIRD cultures and Iranian culture, we intended to test whether the compatibility effect,
208 found in WEIRD cultures, extended also to an Iranian sample.

209 Hypotheses. Based on the reviewed literature, we advanced the following hypotheses:

210 First, we predicted that there would be a difference between congruent and incongruent trials, likely
211 leading to a facilitation of congruent over incongruent trials since the timer started after the
212 sentence was presented.

213 Second, we predicted that action sentences would elicit faster responses compared to abstract ones,
214 in line with the previously discussed results on figurative sentences and on the well-established
215 concreteness effect, showing that concrete words/sentences are processed faster and recalled better
216 than concrete ones (Paivio, 1990; Schwanenflugel, Akin, & Luh, 1992).

217 Third, and more crucially, we advanced the (directional) hypothesis that the congruency action-
218 video with the sentence would be perceived as stronger in the case of concrete sentences, leading to
219 a greater difference in response times between concrete congruent and incongruent trials than
220 between abstract congruent and incongruent trials. As to the cultural and linguistic difference, we
221 advanced two hypotheses, hypothesis four and five. Fourth, we intended to investigate whether the
222 congruency effect we expected to replicate in the Italian sample would be extended or not to a
223 different culture. Finally, we intended to investigate whether using a different language has a
224 different effect with responses to concrete and abstract sentences. We expected the difference
225 between the two languages to be more marked with abstract than with concrete sentences, in line
226 with the idea that linguistic experience is more influential on abstract than on concrete sentences
227 processing (Borghi et al., 2019, 2018).

228

229 **2. Method**

230 **2.1 Sample**

231 Thirty-five Iranian and thirty-eight Italian participants took part in this experiment. All Iranian
232 participants were native Persian speakers (20 females, all but 2 right-handed, mean age 30.5, st dev
233 3.71 range 25-40), had left Iran for less than 8 years, and were now living in Rome (mean age of
234 permanence in Italy 4 years) They were recruited in dorms of Iranian students, or in Iranian meeting
235 points in Rome. Out of the 35 Iranian participants, only 5 spoke fluent Italian. All thirty-eight
236 Italians were Italian native speakers (19 females, all but 2 right-handed, (mean age 26.6 st dev 4.15)
237 range 20-38). All participants had normal or corrected-to-normal vision. The study was in
238 accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the local ethical committee.

239

240 **2.3 Stimuli and Procedure**

241 For the Persian sample, stimuli consisted of fourteen sensible sentences in Persian (see Table 1
242 Panel A). Each sentence was composed of a third-person subject, a transitive verb and a concept
243 noun. In seven sentences, the verbs were used with a concrete meaning, in the other seven the same
244 verb were used in a metaphorical sense. For example, the verb “to pull” was used for the concrete
245 sentence “Kif ra roye zamin ke'id/ She pulled the bag on the floor” and for the abstract sentence
246 “Xane ra be atæ ke'id/She set the house on fire”. Additionally, we combined the verbs with the
247 nouns to create seven meaningless sentences e.g. “tækko ra ruye dærya ke'id/ She pulled the

248 sea”. The word order of Persian sentences is Subject + Object + Verb, which is the unmarked word
 249 order in Persian. The tense is simple past as it contains the simplest process for a third-person
 250 subject with no extra affix added to the verb. Moreover, as both Persian and Italian languages have
 251 the capacity to be meaningful with no subject in the beginning of sentences (pro-drop parameter in
 252 linguistics), the subject is null on the surface. The sentences were selected by asking to 14 Persian
 253 people (age range of 25-43) to rate them through a seven point Likert-scale according to a list of
 254 parameters, useful to determine the degree of abstractness of the sentence (Villani et al., 2019):
 255 concreteness vs abstractness, imageability (Paivio et al., 1986), emotionality (Ponari et al., 2017),
 256 age of acquisition (Barca et al., 2002), modality of acquisition (Marschark, M., & Wauters, 2003),
 257 body-object interaction (Tillotson et al., 2008), social metacognition (Borghi et al., 2018), quantity
 258 of motion, and perceptual strength (Connell & Lynott, 2012; Lynott & Connell, 2013). The
 259 abstract/concrete sentences were compared for different parameters: abstractness/concreteness
 260 [ASentences=3.97 st dev= 0.84; CSentences=1.92 st dev=0.27, $t(6)=-6.99$, $p<.001$], imageability
 261 [ASentences= 4.66 st dev= 0.52; CSentences= 6.42 st dev=0.62, $t(6)=-3.81$, $p<.009$], emotionality,
 262 [ASentences=4.05 st dev= 1.14; CSentences= 3.16 st dev=0.96, $t(5)= 1.20$, $p=.28$], age of
 263 acquisition [ASentences=4.79 st dev=.038; CSentences= 2.93 st dev=0.22, $t(6)=4.81$, $p<.003$],
 264 modality of acquisition [ASentences= 3.83 st dev=0.28; CSentences= 2.48 st dev=.08, $t(6)= 4.27$,
 265 $p<.003$], body-object interaction [ASentences=3.88 st dev= 1.63; CSentences= 1.48 st dev= 0.01,
 266 $t(6)=$, $p<.010$], social metacognition [ASentences= 3.42 st dev= 0.16; CSentences= 1.64 st
 267 dev=0.14, $t(5)=8.15$, $p<.001$], quantity of motion [ASentences=3.70 st dev=1.58; CSentences=
 268 5.12 st dev=0.74, $t(6)=-2.53$, $p<.05$], perceptual strength (hearing) [ASentences=3.94 st dev=0.71;
 269 CSentences= 3.85 st dev 0.76, $t(6)=0.20$, $p= 0.84$], perceptual strength (smelling)
 270 [ASentences=2.09 st dev= 1.35; CSentences= 2.11 st dev=0.80, $t(6)=-0.38$, $p=0.97$], perceptual
 271 strength (touching) [ASentences= 3.57 st dev= 1.57; CSentences=5.09 st dev=0.16, $t(6)=-2.57$,
 272 $p<.05$], perceptual strength (vision) [ASentences=4.36 st dev= 1.16; CSentences= 4.79 st
 273 dev=0.49, $t(6)=$, $p=0.48$], perceptual strength (tasting) [ASentences=1.86 st dev=1.34;
 274 CSentences=1.86 st dev=0.76, $t(6)=$, $p=0.98$] (See Table 2). Three-second video clips showing the
 275 right-hand of an actor performing the action coupled with an object located on the table e.g. (“to
 276 pull the cup on table/to pour the tea/to throw trash”) were recorded. In total there were seven video
 277 clips that represented the action verbs. The action verbs were “to screw”, “to take”, “to throw”, to
 278 pull”, “to pick up”, “to pour” and “to hit”. The sentences could be congruent or incongruent with
 279 respect to the action observed in the video and the verb could have either a concrete or an abstract
 280 metaphorical meaning. When the sentences, either abstract or concrete, contained the action verb
 281 referring to the action observed in the video and they were sensible, the trials were categorized as

282 congruent. On the contrary, when the sentence, either abstract or concrete, contained a verb
 283 referring to an action that differed from the displayed one, the trials were categorized as
 284 incongruent. No sensible sentences were entered as catch trials serving the scope to keep
 285 participants focused on the task. The fourteen sensible sentences were combined with the seven
 286 videos; we thus obtained seven congruent_abstract trials, seven congruent_concrete trials, seven
 287 incongruent_abstract trials and seven incongruent_concrete trials and seven trials consisting of no
 288 sensible sentences. In total seventy trials were randomly administered in two different sessions
 289 composed each one of thirty-five trials.

290 For the Italian sample, stimuli consisted of eighteen sensible Italian sentences (See Table 1 Panel B)
 291 composed of a third-person subject, a transitive verb and a concept noun. Nine of them referred to
 292 concrete contexts e.g. “Lei afferra la tazza/She grasps the cup”, the others nine were metaphorical
 293 sentences e.g. “Lei afferra il concetto/She grasps the concept”, the remaining nine were
 294 meaningless sentences e.g. ”Lei afferra il vulcano/She grasps the volcano”. The sentences were
 295 selected by asking to 17 Italian people (18-51) to rate them through the same seven point Likert-
 296 scale above-mentioned for the Iranian group. The abstract/concrete sentences were compared for
 297 different parameters: abstractness/concreteness [ASentences= 6.16 st dev=0.41; CSentences= 1.71
 298 st dev= 0.41, $t(8)=34.3$, $p<.001$], imageability [ASentences=2.24 st dev= 0.81; CSentences=6.40
 299 st dev=0.23, $t(8)=-13.9$, $p<.001$], emotionality, [ASentences=3.72 st dev=0.77; CSentences= 3.54
 300 st dev=1.58, $t(8)=0.51$, $p=0.62$], age of acquisition [ASentences = 5.08 st dev=0.97;
 301 CSentences=2.91 st dev=0.73, $t(8)= 5.72$, $p<.001$], modality of acquisition [ASentences= 5.54 st
 302 dev=0.22; CSentences= 2.99 st dev=0.86, $t(8)=9.14$, $p<.001$], body-object interaction
 303 [ASentences=6.38 st dev= 1.31; CSentences= 1.88 st dev= 0.46, $t(8)=9.9$, $p<.001$], social
 304 metacognition [ASentences= 2.99 st dev= 0.45; CSentences= 1.33 st dev=0.17, $t(8)=12.48$,
 305 $p<.001$], quantity of motion [ASentences=2.04 st dev=.030; CSentences=5.39 st dev=0.35 $t(8)=-$
 306 19.23, $p<.001$], perceptual strength (hearing) [ASentences=1.89 st dev=.055; CSentences=2.72 st
 307 dev= 1.68, $t(8)=-1.35$, $p=.21$], perceptual strength (smelling) [ASentences=1.26 st dev=0.12;
 308 CSentences=2.09 st dev=1.17, $t(8)=-2.24$, $p=.055$], perceptual strength (touching)
 309 [ASentences=1.36 st dev=0.32; CSentences=4.95 st dev=1.02, $t(8)=-11.32$, $p<.001$], perceptual
 310 strength (vision) [ASentences=1.77 st dev=0.35; CSentences=4.95 st dev=0.60, $t(8)=-14.97$,
 311 $p<.001$], perceptual strength (tasting) [ASentences=1.21 st dev=0.07; CSentences=1.59 st
 312 dev=0.54, $t(8)=-2.05$, $p=0.08$] (See Table 2). The nine action verbs in the video clips were “to
 313 take”, “to grasp”, “to pet”, “to feed”, “to unhinge”, “to hold”, “to pull”, “to divert”, “to squeeze”.
 314 The eighteen sensible sentences were combined with the nine videos in order to have nine

315 congruent_abstract trials, nine congruent_concrete trials, nine incongruent_abstract trials, nine
 316 incongruent_concrete trials and nine trials with no sensible sentences. In total ninety trials were
 317 administered in a random order in two different sessions composed each one of forty-five trials. The
 318 experimental task was administered on a PC utilizing E-Prime software (Version 3). The
 319 participants sat at 60 cm from a 15 inches computer monitor in a dimly lit room. They were asked
 320 to maintain a comfortable position and to keep the feet on a pedal connected with the laptop through
 321 a Multifunctional response box (Chronos PST100430 model). Participants were instructed to look at
 322 a fixation cross that remained on the screen for 1000 ms, then the video started followed by a black
 323 screen lasting 5000 ms. During this time window, participants were asked to perform the
 324 pantomime of the observed action three/four consecutive times. Immediately after, a sentence
 325 lasting 3000 ms appeared on the screen and participants were instructed to press a pedal on the
 326 ground only when the sentence was sensible, otherwise they were asked to refrain from responding.
 327 All participants were informed that their response times (RTs) would be recorded and were invited
 328 to respond as quickly as possible while still maintaining accuracy (Figure 1).

329

330 Table 1 Panel A)

Persian concrete sentences			
	Sentences	Literary meaning	Meaning
1	بچه را زد	S/he hit the child	S/he hit the child
2	کیف را روی زمین کشید	S/he pulled the bag on the floor	S/he pulled the bag on the floor
3	میوه‌ها را از درخت چید	S/he picked the fruits from the tree	S/he picked the fruits from the tree
4	به سبب از پیش گرفت	S/he took an apple from him	S/he took an apple from him
5	زباله را روی زمین انداخت	S/he threw the trash on the floor	S/he threw the trash on the floor
6	لایت را پیچید	S/he screwed the light bulb	S/he screwed the light bulb
7	ظرف‌ها روی زمین ریخت	The plates poured on the floor	The plates poured on the floor
Persian abstract sentences			
	Sentences	Literary meaning	Meaning
1	به استاد ایمیل زد	S/he sent an email to the professor	S/he sent an email to the professor
2	خانه را به آتش کشید	S/he pulled the house to the fire	S/he set the house on fire
3	اسباب خانه را چید	S/he picked up the furniture	S/he decorated the home
4	به بوس از پیش گرفت	S/he got a kiss from him	S/he got a kiss from him
5	اسم او را از قلم انداخت	S/he dropped his/her name	S/he forgot to consider her name
6	میهمانی رُ پیچید	S/he screwed the party	S/he found an excuse to avoid the party
7	آبروش ریخت	Her/his face poured	S/he lost his face

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332

333 Table 1 Panel B)

Italian concrete sentences			
	Sentences	Literary meaning	Meaning
1	Lei/Lui accarezza il cane	S/he caresses the dog	S/he caresses the dog
2	Lei/Lui coglie un fiore	S/he picks a flower	S/he picks a flower
3	Lei/Lui afferra la tazza	S/he grasps the cup	S/he grasps the cup
4	Lei/Lui tira la corda	S/he pulls the rope	S/he pulls the rope
5	Lei/Lui impugna un'arma	S/he holds a weapon	S/he holds a weapon
6	Lei/Lui devia la palla	S/he diverts the ball	S/he diverts the ball
7	Lei/Lui nutre il figlio	S/he feeds the son	S/he feeds the son
8	Lei/Lui scardina la porta	S/he unhinges the door	S/he unhinges the door
9	Lei/Lui stringe una spugna	S/he squeezes the sponge	S/he squeezes the sponge
Italian abstract sentences			
	Sentences	Literary meaning	Meaning
1	Lei/Lui accarezza un'idea	S/he caresses an idea	S/he has an idea
2	Lei/Lui coglie un'occasione	S/he picks an occasion	S/he takes an occasion
3	Lei/Lui afferra un concetto	S/he grasps a concept	S/he grasps a concept
4	Lei/Lui tira le conseguenze	S/he pulls the consequences	S/he draws the consequences
5	Lei/Lui impugna una sentenza	S/he holds a judgment	S/he takes the issue
6	Lei/Lui devia il discorso	S/he diverts a speech	S/he meanders in a topic
7	Lei/Lui nutre un dubbio	S/he feeds a doubt	S/he has the doubts
8	Lei/Lui scardina un'accusa	S/he unhinges an accusation	S/he thwarts an accusation
9	Lei/Lui stringe un'amicizia	S/he squeezes a friendship	S/he holds a friend

334
 335 Experiment's sentences selected in the Persian (Panel A) and Italian (Panel B) sample.

336 Table 2)

	Italian sample		Persian sample	
	Concrete	Abstract	Concrete	Abstract
ABSTRACTNESS/CONCRETENESS	1.71 sd= 0.41	6.16 sd=0.41 *	1.92 sd=0.27	3.97 sd= 0.84*
IMAGEABILITY	6.40 sd=0.23	2.24 sd= 0.81*	6.42 sd=0.62	4.66 sd= 0.52*
EMOTIONALITY	3.54 sd=1.58	3.72 sd=0.77	3.16 sd=0.96	4.05 sd= 1.14
AGE OF ACQUISITION	2.91 sd=0.73	5.08 sd=0.97*	2.93 sd=0.22	4.79 sd=.038*
MODALITY OF ACQUISITION	2.99 sd=0.86	5.54 sd=0.22*	2.48 sd=0.08	3.83 sd=0.28*
BODY-OBJECT INTERACTION	1.88 sd=0.46	6.38 sd= 1.31*	1.48 sd= 0.01	3.88 sd= 1.63*
SOCIAL METACOGNITION	1.33 sd=0.17	2.99 sd= 0.45*	1.64 sd=0.14	3.42 sd= 0.16*
QUANTITY OF MOTION	5.39 sd=0.35	2.04 sd=.030*	5.12 sd=0.74	3.70 sd=1.58*
PERCEPTUAL STRENGTH HEARING	2.72 sd=1.68	1.89 sd=.055	3.85 sd= 0.76	3.94 sd=0.71
PERCEPTUAL STRENGTH SMELLING	2.09 sd =1.17	1.26 sd=0.12	2.11 sd=0.80	2.09 sd=1.35
PERCEPTUAL STRENGTH TOUCHING	4.95 sd=1.02	1.36 sd=0.32*	5.09 sd=0.16	3.57 sd= 1.57*
PERCEPTUAL STRENGTH VISION	4.95 sd=0.60	1.77 sd=0.35*	4.79 sd=0.49	4.36 sd= 1.16
PERCEPTUAL STRENGTH TASTING	1.59 sd=0.54	1.21 sd=0.07	1.86 sd=0.76	1.86 sd=1.34

337
 338 Averaged scores along all the psycholinguistic dimensions for concrete and abstract sentences in the Italian and Persian
 339 sample,

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341

342 Figure 1)

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344 Experimental procedure: Participants were instructed to look at a fixation cross for 1000 ms. During a time window of
 345 5000 ms participants were asked to perform the pantomime of the observed action. Immediately after, a sentence
 346 appeared on the screen and participants were instructed to press a pedal on the ground only when the sentence was
 347 sensible, otherwise they were asked to refrain from responding.

348

349 3. Results

350 The analysis was restricted to 4034 reaction times. The analyses we performed in the sentence
 351 sensibility task were restricted to the sensible sentence, the non-sensible sentences were not
 352 included because they were not informative for the experimental question, indeed their role was just
 353 to keep the attention on the task and to make the task implicit. Hence, all the errors we reported
 354 refer to false negative (thinking that the sentence is without sense when it is not the case). From the
 355 overall possible responses, we discarded 662 trials which were not given responses. Among all the
 356 errors, 493 (74.5 %) involved abstract sentences, the remaining 169 (25.5 %) were related to
 357 concrete sentences. Such percentage discrepancy clearly indicates that in the sensibility task the
 358 abstract sentences were perceived as more complex than the concrete sentences. Following a
 359 stepwise procedure, in the first model we included fixed effects for the variables Congruency,
 360 Category, Group and we added random intercepts for Participants and the Sentences nested in the
 361 Participants factor. In a second, third and fourth models, we excluded in the following order the
 362 variables: Congruency (congruent, incongruent), Category (abstract, concrete), Group (Italians,

363 Persians), in order to investigate the main effect of each factor. In the fifth, sixth, and seventh
 364 model, we investigated the two-way interactions with the addition of all the fixed factors.
 365 Specifically, in model fifth we entered the interaction Category x Congruency, in the sixth model
 366 the interaction Congruency x Group, and in seventh model the interaction Category x Group. We
 367 constantly kept in all the models the random intercepts for Participants and Sentences nested in the
 368 Participants factor. Finally, in eighth model we entered the three-way interaction Group x
 369 Congruency x Category. We compared the eighth model with all these models. Model eight was the
 370 one with the best fit (see Table 3), suggesting that the three-way interaction better explained the
 371 data. This model yielded a significant main effect of the Category ($F(1,3215)=14.6683$, $p=.0001$)
 372 due to the fact that overall abstract sentences showed slower RTs (1481, $SE=38.3$) than concrete
 373 sentences (1456, $SE=38.2$) (Concreteness effect, Hypothesis 2). The main effect of the Congruency
 374 was also approaching the significance ($F(1,3216)=3.3403$, $p=0.0677$), congruent conditions (1486,
 375 $SE=38.2$) were slower than incongruent conditions (1451, $SE=38.2$). Both main effects are
 376 however qualified by the interactions. The 3-way interaction Group X Congruency X Category was
 377 significant ($F(1,3215)=7.1218$, $p=0.0077$) (Figure 2). In the Italian group, Tukey post hoc
 378 comparisons indicate that in the congruent condition, concrete sentences (1372, $SE=53.7$) were
 379 processed faster than abstract sentences (1534, $SE=54.4$), ($t(3216)=7.26$ $p<.0001$). The same
 380 difference was present in the incongruent condition: concrete sentences (1433, $SE=53.8$) were
 381 processed faster than abstract sentences, even if the effect was less marked (1505, $SE=54.2$),
 382 ($t(3216)=3.23$ $p=.0273$). In the Italian sample our hypothesis that a concreteness effect would exist
 383 was thus confirmed (Hypothesis 2). Moreover, Tukey post hoc comparisons show that, in keeping
 384 with our predictions, concrete sentences (1372, $SE=53.7$) were processed faster in the congruent
 385 than in the incongruent condition (1433, $SE=53.8$), although this difference was just approaching
 386 the significance ($t(3216)=-2.923$, $p=.0685$), suggesting a tendency towards a facilitation effect
 387 (Hypothesis 3).

388 In contrast with the Italian group, in the Persian group, Tukey post hoc comparisons indicate that
 389 abstract sentences (1476, $SE=56.8$) were processed faster than concrete sentences in the congruent
 390 condition (1562, $SE=56.9$), ($t(739)=-3.17$ $p=.0336$), while the difference between abstract sentences
 391 (1409, $SE=57.0$) and concrete ones (1457, $SE=56.9$) was not significant in the incongruent
 392 condition, ($t(739)=-1.79$ $p=.6267$). Furthermore, concrete sentences (1562, $SE=56.9$) were
 393 processed significantly slower in the congruent than in the incongruent condition (1457, $SE=56.9$)
 394 ($t(3216)=4.072$, $p=.0012$). Abstract sentences (1476, $SE=56.8$) in the congruent condition, instead,
 395 were not processed significantly slower than abstract ones in the incongruent condition (1409,

396 SE=57.0), ($t(3216)=2.627$, $p=.1464$). The results show an inhibition effect, driven by the concrete
397 sentences.

398 All the other Tukey Post hoc comparisons between the Italian and Persian groups were not
399 significant ($p>.2461$).

400 The 3-way interaction can be better qualified by the significant 2-way interaction Group x Category
401 ($F(1,739)=51.33$, $p<.0001$) Figure 3) and by the 2-way significant interaction Group x Congruency
402 ($F(1, 3216)=20.14$, $p<.0001$) Figure 4).

403 In the 2-way Group x Category interaction, Tukey Post Hoc comparisons indicate that in the Italian
404 group, concrete sentences (1403, SE=52.7) were processed significantly faster than abstract
405 sentences (1520, SE=53.0) ($t(3216)=7.36$, $p<.0001$) (concreteness effect, Hypothesis 2). On the
406 contrary, in the Persian group, Tukey post hoc comparisons show that abstract sentences (1442,
407 SE=55.4) were processed significantly faster than concrete sentences (1510, SE=55.4), ($t(739)=-$
408 3.32, $p=.0052$). In the 2-way Group x Congruency interaction, Tukey post hoc comparisons indicate
409 that in the Italian group there was no difference between the congruent (1453, SE= 52.8) and the
410 incongruent condition (1469, SE= 52.8), ($t(3216)=-1.006$, $p=.7461$). Crucially, in the Persian group
411 the sentences were processed significantly slower in the congruent condition (1519, SE=55.2) than
412 in the incongruent condition (1433, SE= 55.2), ($t(3216)=4.74$, $p<.0001$), showing the inhibition
413 effect.

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426 Table 3)

		Information criteria		
		AIC	BIC	-2LL
First Model	Fixed Effects Group, Congruency, Category Random Effects Participant/sentence	59771.48	59815.60	-29878.74
Second Model	Fixed Effects Group, Category Random Effects Participant/sentence	59772.72	59810.54	-29880.36
Third Model	Fixed Effects Group, Congruency Random Effects Participant/sentence	59784.45	59822.26	-29886.22
Fourth Model	Fixed Effects Category, Congruency Random Effects Participant/sentence	59769.56	59807.37	-29878.78
Fifth Model	Fixed Effects Group, Category * Congruency Random Effects Participant/sentence	59770.54	59820.96	-29877.27
Sixth Model	Fixed Effects Category, Group * Congruency Random Effects Participant/sentence	59754.12	59804.54	-29869.06
Seventh Model	Fixed Effects Congruency, Group * Category Random Effects Participant/sentence	59723.08	59773.50	-29853.54
Eighth Model	Fixed Effects Group* Category* Congruency Random Effects Participant/sentence	59700.00	59769.33	-29839.00

AIC) Akaike's information criterion; BIC) Schwarz's Bayesian criterion; -2LL) -2 log-likelihood

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Information criteria on the linear mixed models performed on the entire sample.

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434 Figure 2)

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436 The graph shows the predicted values of the outcome variables in the all the combinations included in the model.
 437 Shaded bands represent the confidence intervals (95%).

438 Congruency condition: in the Italian sample concrete sentences were processed significantly faster than abstract
 439 sentences; in the Persian sample abstract sentences were processed significantly faster than concrete sentences.

440 Incongruency condition: in the Italian sample concrete sentences were processed significantly faster than abstract
 441 sentences; in the Persian sample RTs of concrete and abstract sentences did not differ.

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453 Figure 3)

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456 The graph shows the predicted values of the outcome variables in the all the combinations included in the model

457 Shaded bands represent the confidence intervals (95%).

458 Group* Congruency interaction: in the Italian sample there was no difference between the congruent and incongruent

459 condition; in the Persian sample stimuli were processed significantly faster in the incongruent than in the congruent

460 condition.

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467 Figure 4)

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469 The graph shows the predicted values of the outcome variables in the all the combinations included in the model

470 Shaded bands represent the confidence intervals (95%).

471 Group* Category interaction: in the Italian sample concrete sentences were processed significantly faster than abstract

472 sentences; in the Persian sample abstract sentences were processed significantly faster than concrete sentences.

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475 4. Discussion

476 The results clearly show that action sentences are grounded in action, even if the extent of their

477 grounding differs as a function of the abstractness level. More crucially, the marked differences

478 between Iranians and Italians are food for thought and induce a reflection. In the next pages, we will

479 first summarize the main results and the main differences between the two groups, then

480 provide/attempt some possible explanations.

481 Before summarizing the data, a caveat. The fact that the Iranians who participated to the study had
482 been exposed to the Italian language and culture might constitute a potential limitation of this work.
483 However, all our participants were late bilinguals, only 5 of 35 spoke fluent Italian, and they
484 frequented mostly Iranians. Furthermore, research on bilinguals show that they have a flexible
485 linguistic organization (e.g. Athanasopoulos, & Avelledo, 2012). When tested in their own language,
486 participants tend to revert to the structures used in their own language. For example, Chinese
487 bilinguals tend to use more taxonomic conceptual relations when they speak in English, more
488 thematic ones when they speak in Chinese (Li-Jun, Zhang, & Nisbett, 2004). In addition, age had a
489 marked effect of the degree of cognitive shift toward the L2, as revealed by studies on time
490 (Boroditsky, 2001), and all our participants arrived in Italy when they were adults. Based on these
491 considerations, we think that the exposure to the Italian language and culture might not have
492 markedly influenced the results. However, future research should shed better light on the possible
493 fine-grained distinctions between the performance of Iranians living in Iran and Iranian living
494 elsewhere.

495 **Italians:** The predicted congruency effect (**Hypothesis 1**) was not present/not significant **per se but**
496 **it was modulated by the interaction with Category in the three-way interaction.** In line with
497 our expectations, evaluating the matching between the action and the sentence was easier for
498 concrete than for abstract sentences (Hypothesis 2, concreteness effect); this advantage of concrete
499 over abstract sentences was present both for the congruent and the incongruent condition, but was
500 slightly more marked in the congruent condition, in line with our predictions (Hypothesis 3).

501 **Iranians:** The pattern of results of Iranian participants did not match that of Italians; surprisingly, it
502 was quite different. First of all, a reverse congruency effect was significant, indicating that the
503 congruent condition was slower than the incongruent one; furthermore, the advantage of concrete
504 congruent trials we found in the Italian sample was not extended to the Persian culture. Hence, the
505 hypothesis that the congruency and concreteness effects would be extended to the Persian sample
506 was not confirmed (Hypothesis 4).

507 Furthermore, in the congruent condition abstract sentences were processed faster than concrete
508 ones. This profoundly differs from what happens in the Italian sample: as figure 2 clearly shows, in
509 the Persian sample the condition with slowest response times is that of concrete congruent trials, i.e.
510 the faster condition in the Italian sample. Apparently, when reading a sentence, Iranians simulate
511 the mentioned action; this simulation interferes with the actions they observe and perform,
512 generating an inhibition in the congruent condition. This inhibition is particularly marked with

513 concrete sentences, consistently with the fact that they are grounded to a greater extent in the
514 sensorimotor system, but is present also with abstract sentences. Even if in the incongruent
515 condition abstract and concrete sentences did not differ, through a visual inspection of the data we
516 notice that the fastest RTs are elicited by incongruent abstract sentences, i.e. by the cases in which
517 the sensorimotor system is less activated.

518 As to Hypothesis 5, we did not confirm our expectations that the difference across the two
519 languages would be more marked for abstract than for the concrete sentences.

520 Overall, the comparison between the two samples allow us to advance some considerations:

521 1) For Italians, it seems that language and action are quite integrated, while for Iranians they are
522 processed separately. The inhibition found in the Iranian sample might reflect an overload due to
523 the fact that the motor system is activated by the video/movement and that this exerts a priming
524 effect on the motor activation evoked by the sentence.

525 .

526 2) The distinction between concrete and abstract sentences seems to be more marked in Italian than
527 Iranian participants. In the Italian sample we found a facilitation with concrete sentences in both the
528 congruent and incongruent condition, and an opposite pattern with abstract sentences; in contrast, in
529 the Persian sample **the 3-way interaction shows that in the congruent condition** abstract
530 sentences were processed faster than concrete ones, while in the incongruent condition no
531 difference was present between concrete and abstract sentences. The higher continuity between
532 concrete and abstract sentences can be owing to the fact that Persian is more a literary/metaphoric
533 language (poems, literature, etc.), and also that abstract sentences in Persian seem to be more
534 embodied than in Italian, i.e. concrete and abstract sentences seem to rely on a common scheme to a
535 larger extent than in Italian.

536 Seyed Ghorab (2012), referring to the role and importance of metaphor and figurative speech in the
537 Persian language from the very old times declares "metaphors are the heart of Persian poetry. They
538 are used for a wide range of purposes in different genres". He argues that the poet's professional
539 survival rests on their ability to contrive original metaphors within the established literary
540 conventions. As metaphor is very important in poetry for Persians, it has entered in the ordinary life
541 of people, since poetry is considered one of the most significant artistic achievement of Persia (e.g.
542 Yarshater, 1962). You easily can trace variations of everyday talk of people in poems of old famous
543 poets such as, Khayam (1048-1131), Rumi(1207-1273), Hafez (1325-1389), who are not only
544 famous in Iran but internationally appreciated. In sum, some metaphoric expressions have entered
545 in the life of Iranian people and have become independent from the concrete meaning they

546 originally are extracted from. You can even trace the Persian sentences of the experiments of this
547 paper in the poems of Hafez or Rumi. For instance, once hearing the sentence “Xane ra be
548 atattke□id/” (literary “to pull the house on the fire”) which means to set the house on fire, Persians
549 immediately think of the action of burning, not of pulling.

550 A further reason of the differences in the factor Category can be owing to differences of Perceptual
551 Strength across the two languages. Notice that in the two groups there was a difference in
552 Perceptual Strength: abstract and concrete sentences differed only for touching in the Persian set
553 while they differed also for vision in the Italian set. To verify whether differences in Perceptual
554 Strength across the two languages might affect the results, we run mixed model analyses. The
555 analyses are reported in the Appendix. Overall, our results indicate an important role of perceptual
556 strength, in line with the hypothesis of Connell & Lynott (2012). Across the two groups we found
557 that an increase in perceptual strength led to faster response times. However, perceptual strength
558 differently influences the two languages: it loaded more on concrete items in the Persian sample,
559 more on abstract items in the Italian sample. This different role of perceptual strength might thus
560 contribute to explain the differences in the concreteness effect, which was present in the Italian
561 sample but not in the Persian one (See Appendix).

562 It remains to be explained why with concrete congruent sentences we find an inhibition in Persian
563 but a tendency towards facilitation in the Italian sample. The reason underlying contradictory
564 results – interference and facilitation – has been extensively debated in the literature on action-
565 language integration. A possible reason underlying such contradictory results lies in the timing:
566 interference seems to occur between 160 and 500 ms after stimulus presentation, whereas
567 facilitation becomes evident between 550 and 800 ms after sentence appearance (Borreggine &
568 Kaschak, 2006; Boulenger et al., 2006; de Vega, Robertson, Glenberg, Kaschak, & Rinck, 2004).
569 The model by Chersi et al. (2010), based on a network with a chain organization, explains the
570 divergent results on language and effectors in terms of timing of motor chains activations. The early
571 interference is due to the fact that the motor system is activated concurrently by the sentence and by
572 the movement; the late facilitation is another manifestation of the same process, i.e. an aftereffect of
573 this early overload of the motor system (Chersi et al., 2010). Results found by Liepelt et al. (2012)
574 are convergent with this model: participants were required to execute a hand opening or closing
575 action in response to the color (blue or red) of the words “open” and “close”. Seeing the word
576 automatically evoked a gesture, leading to an advantage of congruent trials (word open-opening
577 gesture). The same results were obtained in further experiments in which participants were required
578 to say “open” or “close” in response to a green or a red cue displayed above a human hand
579 performing either an opening or a closing action. The results matched those of the first experiment:

580 congruent trials are faster than not congruent ones, consistently demonstrating that there is a
581 bidirectional crosstalk between language and motor system. A neutral condition was then added, in
582 which a hand remained stationary during the task. Results confirm this showing that semantically
583 non-corresponding action word pairings lead to interference, consistently with the model by Chersi
584 et al. (2010) that predicts interference when action and language are simultaneously processed, and
585 facilitation in case of delayed processing.

586 In our study, the contradictory results cannot be ascribed to overall timing, since the exposure time
587 is the same for Italians and Iranians.

588 Two possible explanations of the contradictory results are possible. The first reflects a linguistic
589 difference between Italian and Persian. In the Persian sentences the verb is placed at the end of the
590 sentence, in contrast in Italian it is located immediately after the subject. Such grammatical
591 difference could have contributed to create in the Persian sample a shorter temporal interval
592 between the simulation of the action triggered by the sentence and the motor response than in the
593 Italian sample. Dennison and Bergen (2010) provided this explanation for the interference result
594 they found with an ACE paradigm in Korean. We are not inclined to favour this explanation because
595 we considered the congruency between the simulation induced by the video and that elicited by the
596 sentence – in this case, in the Persian sample the distance is longer. Furthermore, Dennison and
597 Bergen used an ACE paradigm in which sentence and motor responses were concurrent, while we
598 did not.

599 A plausible explanation of the inhibition we found in the Iranian sample is owing to the fact that
600 information derived from language and from vision/action are scarcely related and need to be
601 integrated online, generating an overload. In this respect, Estes et al. (2015) provides an explanation
602 of spatial interference that can be useful for us. They asked participants to identify related or
603 unrelated visual targets above or below a cue word that had high or low spatial associations (e.g.
604 cloud vs. puddle). They found a facilitation when the target was related to the cue, and interference
605 when they were not related. A similar explanation has been offered by Kaschak et al. (2005), who
606 ascribed the interference effect found when participants listened to sentences and simultaneously
607 observed black and white displays moving in the same/opposite direction to a different degree of
608 “integrability”, i.e. to the extent to which the perceptual stimuli can be integrated with the content
609 of the sentence. For example, a picture of a car can be easily integrated with the content of the
610 sentence “The car approached you,” whereas the black-and-white stimuli used could not, thus
611 generated interference. Hence, when the visual/motor stimulus match with the verbal one there is a

612 facilitation, when they do not, or they cannot be easily integrated, then there is an interference.
613 Following this interpretation, it seems that in Persian action and language are separately coded and
614 need to be integrated online, requiring resources and time. Conversely, in Italian action and
615 language are easily integrated online, thus we find a tendency towards facilitation in concrete
616 sentences. But which is the reason of this difference between Italians and Iranians? One possibility
617 is that it depends on factors related to the specificities of the two languages – for example, the
618 writing direction is opposite (left-to-right in Italian and right-to-left in Persian), and as a
619 consequence, there might be a different hemispheric action-language lateralization in the two
620 languages. Furthermore, the orthography is more transparent in Italian than in Persian. However, it
621 seems unlikely that such inhibition/facilitation depends on merely linguistic factors. The most
622 plausible explanations we came up with relied on the gesture-language system. The Italian gesture
623 system is more structured and more integrated with language compared to the Persian one. A wide
624 literature shows that, compared to other populations, Italians have a rich gesture vocabulary, and
625 produce a lot of gestures in everyday communication (Colletta et al., 2015); notably, the Italian
626 gesture system is particularly structured and includes many conventional gestures (De Jorio, 2000;
627 Diadori, 1990; Efron, 1941; Kendon, 2004; Munari & Saglietti, 1994) (but see (Pettenati, Sekine,
628 Congestrì, & Volterra, 2012) showing that this Italian specificity does not characterize children). As
629 to Persian, using gestures has been for long banished. Nowadays in Iran, moving hands is accepted
630 and even common, especially in academic spaces. However, until the last decades moving hands
631 while talking was considered impolite as it was the sign of getting control and authority in a
632 discourse. Elderly people would get annoyed to see a younger person move hands in a conversation
633 with them and they hardly would do it themselves. Even nowadays, when people and especially
634 men intend to show their respect for authoritative others, they put one hand on another hand and
635 take them before their body. The tendency to avoid moving hands when talking with others or
636 sitting beside people with higher authority could have roots in religious believes considering
637 quotes from the Prophets and Imams that advise people to have control on their body to respect
638 others. For instance, Imam Sadegh says "Do not look at your parents' eye unless with kindness; do
639 not let your voice get higher than theirs; do not let your hands go upper than their hand; and never
640 walk before them (Majlisi, 1986:79)." The governmental religious website, which is
641 promulgating Islamic ways of communication, declares that according to Islamic etiquette you
642 would better not to imply anything through your eye, eyebrow or hand when talking (Tebyan,
643 2017). Around two decades ago children were told to sit with their hands on their knees without
644 moving in family gatherings, and in the classroom when teachers asked them to go in front of the
645 blackboard to answer questions the polite position was standing with their hands on the side. In

646 addition, when sitting on their bench or chair the polite position was putting their hands on knees or
647 in folded arms style to prevent any movement. The habit to repress gestures and movements while
648 talking can be the cause of the inhibition we found: the linguistic and action systems would be
649 difficult to integrate, hence require more time when simultaneously activated.

650

651 Conclusion

652 We performed two experiments aimed at investigating the cross-talk between concrete and abstract
653 action sentences and videos representing them in two different cultures/languages, the Italian and
654 the Iranian one. The results confirm the tight relationship between language and action, stronger for
655 concrete than for abstract sentences. Strikingly, the results reveal a marked cultural/linguistic
656 difference: while observing a video and imitating an action inhibits concrete congruent sentences in
657 the Iranian sample, it leads to a trend towards facilitation of the same ones in the Italian sample.
658 The results can be ascribed to the higher integration between gestures and language in Italians, and
659 to the tendency to avoid movement when talking widespread in Iranians. Overall, our results help to
660 shed light on the possible causes of facilitation/interference-inhibition and suggest that taking into
661 account of the culture to which participants belong is of paramount importance to understand in
662 depth the mechanisms responsible for contrasting results.

663

664

665 Appendix

666 To understand the possible role Perceptual Strength exerts on our results, we computed a normalized index for each sentence
667 weighted on the range of values attributed to all the abstract/concrete sentences within each perceptual component (vision, touch,
668 smell, taste, hear) in the entire sample. We averaged the weighted indexes in order to obtain a unique value of Perceptual Strength
669 ranging from 0 to 1 for each Italian and Persian sentence. We adopted a stepwise procedure, as those already described in the
670 manuscript. We maintained as random intercepts participants and sentences and we combined in 51 models all the possible
671 combinations of the fixed factors and their two way/ three-way interactions with the covariate. The high number of models was
672 obtained because we considered the two-interactions and the three-way interactions among all the factors and we eliminated from the
673 model each factor following a stepwise procedure. We compared all these models with a full model expressed by the interaction of
674 the Group, Congruency, Category and Perceptual Strength with the addition of all the fixed factors and as random effects the
675 participants and the sentence. Such model resulted to be the best compared with the others. The model yielded a significant four-way
676 interaction Group X Category X Congruency X Perceptual Strength ($F(1,3210)=4.52$, $p=0.0336$). In order to explore the four-way
677 interaction, we performed two separate analyses, one for each sample. In the Italian sample, following a stepwise procedure, we
678 compared 15 models with Congruency, Category and Perceptual Strength as fixed factors and their interaction, again participants and
679 sentences were included as random factors. The best model was the full model expressed by the interaction Congruency X Category
680 X Perceptual Strength. This model yielded a significant main effect of the Category ($F(1,1961)= 60.87$ $p<.0001$). Both the two-way
681 interaction Congruency X Category ($F(1,1961)= 8.857$ $p=0.003$) and the two-way interaction Perceptual Strength X Category (Figure
682 A) were significant ($F(1,1961)= 17.61$ $p=0.006$). Crucially, the three-way interaction Congruency X Category X Perceptual Strength
683 was also significant ($F(1,1961)=7.39$, $p=0.0066$) (Figure B). In the Persian sample, we followed the identical stepwise procedure
684 adopted in the Italian sample, and we compared again 15 models. The best model was again the full model expressed by the fixed
685 factors and their interaction Congruency X Category X Perceptual Strength; in which participants and sentences were included as
686 random intercepts. This model yielded a significant main effect of the Category ($F(1,433)= 9.21$ $p=.0025$) and of the Congruency

687 (F(1,1249)= 16.71 p<0.0001). The two-way interaction Perceptual Strength X Category was significant (F(1,433)= 11.69 p=0.0007)
 688 (Figure C) and the two-way interaction Congruency X Perceptual Strength resulted significant (F(1,1249)= 28.20 p<.0001) (Figure
 689 D) as well. Crucially, the three-way interaction Congruency, Category and Perceptual Strength was not significant (F(1,1249)=
 690 0.2352 p=.6278).

691 Figure A)

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694

695 Italian sample- Perceptual Strength strongly modulates the facilitation effect in the Abstract sentences: small Perceptual strength
 696 increments drastically reduce the RTs in Abstract sentences. Concrete sentences are instead not modulated by Perceptual Strength.
 697

698

699 Figure B)

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702

703 Italian sample- Perceptual strength strongly modulates the facilitation effect in Abstract sentences: small increments in Perceptual
 704 strength drastically reduce the RTs in Abstract sentences in the congruent condition. Concrete sentences show instead an opposite
 705 trend: RTs are slower, the more Perceptual Strength increases. In the incongruent condition, there is no difference between
 706 processing Abstract and Concrete sentences: the graphs show a general facilitation in the responses at the increase of Perceptual
 707 strength.
 708

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711
712 Figure C)
713

714

715 Persian sample- Perceptual strength strongly modulates the facilitation effect in Concrete sentences: small Perceptual strength
716 increments drastically reduce RTs in Concrete sentences. Processing of Abstract sentences, instead is not modulated by Perceptual
717 Strength.
718

719
720 Figure D)

721

722 Persian sample- Perceptual strength strongly modulates the facilitation effect in the congruent condition: small Perceptual strength
723 increments drastically reduce RTs in the congruent condition. In the incongruent condition, instead, RTs slow down with Perceptual
724 Strength increments.
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728 **Open Practices Statement**

729 The raw data for all analyses are available at:

730 **<https://osf.io/w3m7t/>**

731

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